

Sugammadex and Hormonal Contraceptives: Improving Documentation and Education

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Background

- Muscle paralysis helps facilitate endotracheal intubation and aids in various surgeries to help optimize the surgical field
- Neuromuscular blocking agents (NMBAs) will produce muscle paralysis
- Duration of action of NMBAs is variable and can exceed the length of the surgery (residual neuromuscular blockade is estimated to be as high as 20-65%)
- Residual neuromuscular blockade or inadequate NMBA reversal can lead to various complications
- Sugammadex reverses NMBAs and is faster, more predictable, and does not have common side effects compared to older agents; however, usage equates to one missed dose of oral contraceptives

Purpose

To improve counseling for reproductive age female patients about the decrease in efficacy of hormonal contraceptives with Sugammadex administration and to improve documentation of these interactions in the EMR

Review of Literature

- Sugammadex can decrease etonogestrel (progesterin commonly found in birth control) up to 34%, presenting a problem for efficacy of contraceptives
- Accurate documentation is essential aspect of healthcare, may prevent the risk of adverse outcomes
- Two retrospective chart reviews = no patient who received Sugammadex w/documented counseling on Sugammadex's effect on oral contraceptives in health record
- Computerized clinical decision support (CDS) tools effectively identify missing documentation and alert providers
- CDS alerts positively impact patient safety and outcomes

Methods

- The Iowa Model systematically guided project
- Completed at Kaiser Permanente South Bay Medical Center
- Development of an intraoperative CDS tool providers would encounter on the EMR when Sugammadex administered
- Patient Instruction Note, will include "smart text" option that automatically fills out an instruction note that would appear in the patient's discharge summary
- Collaboration with EPIC engineers to create a CDS tool and SmartText that provides the patient with education regarding Sugammadex and alternative contraceptives
- An in-service was provided to perioperative staff to educate about:
 - Goals/aim of the DNP project
 - New CDS tool
 - Interaction between Sugammadex and hormonal contraceptives
- Participants included 42 anesthesiologists, nurse anesthetists, and PACU nurses
- Pre-and post-test questionnaires were administered to assess the effectiveness of intervention

Results

- Q1: I knew Sugammadex decreases the efficacy of hormonal contraceptives (p<0.05)
- Q2: I routinely educate patients on alternative contraception if they have received Sugammadex (p=0.097)
- Q3: I routinely document my education on alternative contraceptive use to patients who received Sugammadex (p=0.740)
- Q4: It is easy to Provide patients with information about Sugammadex (p=0.088)
- Q5: I am comfortable educating patients on Sugammadex (p=0.065)

Results, cont.

Limitations

- Transferability of the results may be limited
- Threat of maturation
- Small sample size

Recommendations

- Future research is recommended to include multiple morning staff meetings to increase sample sizes
- Longer timeframe between pre-and post-test evaluation

Conclusion

- There was a significant difference in the response to question one (p<0.05)
- Responses to questions two, four, and five did show a trend toward significance
- Increase in knowledge about the interaction between Sugammadex and hormonal contraceptives shown
- More research is needed to determine if a significant change in practice occurred